

Role Of Green Infrastructure in Enhancing Mental Health

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Abstract:

Green infrastructure plays very important role in enhancing mental health. Green spaces have very positive effect on physical, mental and social health. Green spaces have very positive effect on physical, mental and social health. Green spaces are associated to reduce stress, anxiety, depression. This paper reviews evidence of how green infrastructure helps to good mental health.

Keywords: Infrastructure, Environment, Lifestyle, Mental Health

Introduction:

Due to growth of urbanization and today's hectic life style the incidents of mental illness has increased significantly. Green infrastructure is the natural and built green spaces that use nature to manage variety of challenges including improving air quality, water quality, providing wildlife habitat. It provides other benefits like social, economic and environmental benefits. Many diseases like, heart disease, cancer, cerebrovascular disease, chronic diseases and injury are product of unhealthy environment and sedentary lifestyle.

Definition of Green infrastructure:

Green infrastructure means- a strategic, planned network of natural, semi natural and artificial plant and water components designed and managed to deliver a wide range of ecosystem services. Green infrastructure include gardens, rivers, private parks, street trees.

Definition of Mental Health:

Mental health is a state of well-being in which an individual realizes their potential, can cope with normal life stresses, works productively

and contributes to their community. – World Health Organization

Mental Health and Green infrastructure:

Green infrastructure like parks, trees and green spaces provide peaceful atmosphere to the people. Green spaces motivate outdoor activities and it also strengthen social ties with people. It can be used to reduce stress among neighbours. Mental health problems become one of the causes of diseases and disability. It is the need of time to create safe and protect mental health. Green infrastructure plays very important role in this mission.

Urbanization has increased the importance of green infrastructure. Time spent in the green atmosphere reduces cortisol level and other physical stress level which are reasons of many diseases. It improves concentration. It was provided in the study at Denmark that higher level of green spaces in childhood is associated with a lower risk of wide variety of psychiatric disorders from adolescence to adulthood. Time spent in the company of trees promotes physical exercise and social interactions. Physical exercise and social interactions increase feeling of calm lower heart rate, blood pressure, stress hormones.

It mitigate environmental stressors such as urban noise and poor air quality.

Availability of green spaces create more chances for people of physical activities and relaxation at green spaces. People feel kind of meditation at the green parks due to their hectic daily busy routine. People improve their mood and attention at green spaces They may be used as therapeutic spaces for rehabilitative exercise for persons with coronary artery disease and have been associated with lower rate of diseases like type 2 diabetes.

There are many researches which proves that people use green spaces to be serene, social were they have greater restorative effects. Green environment improves self esteem and mood of the people

Other benefits of Green Infrastructure:

Green spaces provide environmental benefits through their effects on reducing heat, offsetting greenhouse gas emissions and attenuating storm water. In urban area green infrastructure provide space for physical activities and social interactions as there is limitations of open space in urban areas. Most of the children activities have chances at green spaces. Obesity and mental illness can be cured or its effect can be reduce in the company of green spaces. It is product of urbanization and hectic lifestyle. People can get relaxation at green spaces or infrastructure.

Green spaces are important at urban areas due to many reasons as it social spaces and areas for recreation and cultural togetherness, economic and environmental purpose. Because of the considering benefits of green spaces at urban areas there is growing awareness of keeping spaces for green infrastructure at urban areas.

Social interaction with neighbours and other people create secure and peaceful environment as there is informal conversation at

parks. Green spaces provide environmental benefits as it reduces heat, greenery minimizes air, water and noise pollution and offset greenhouse gas emissions through Co2 absorption. Greenery also provide storm water attenuation acting as a measure for flood mitigation. Ecological benefits include preservation of biodiversity and nature conservation.

Conclusion:

Green infrastructure is very important in rural and also at urban areas. Its availability, size and quality matter in the benefits of it. Green spaces are used in variety of way by the people. It must be planned that green spaces should be used for physical and mental health of the people. It enable people for social interaction and entertainment. Green infrastructure is not only seen as beautification but also as public health necessity. It is proved in many researches that green spaces improves emotional wellbeing, support mental restoration and strengthens bond in society. It helps to reduce mental stress burden and enhance healthy and quality life for people.

There is urgent need of accessible and effective green infrastructure for improvement of mental health. It is said that environment shape human behaviour. Green infrastructure make very positive behaviour and psychological effect on the people who spent more time in the company of green spaces. Green spaces are used as therapeutic interventions for youth at risk, individuals living with dementia and stressed employees. It may include social and therapeutic horticulture, nature based arts and crafts, animal assisted interventions. In short, green infrastructure provide vital benefits for mental and physical health and it is need of time to provide it in rural and urban areas for wellbeing of the people.

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